

HIGH TEMPERATURE OXIDATION KINETICS OF A SiC-WHISKER REINFORCED Al_2O_3

Wang Deqing and Hugo F. Lopez
Materials Department
College of Engineering and Applied Science
University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee
Milwaukee, WI 53201

ABSTRACT

In this work the thermal oxidation resistance of a 30 vol% SiC whisker reinforced Al_2O_3 in air at 1300-1500°C was investigated. Rates of weight gain and of scale thickening were measured and activation energies were found from Arrhenius plots. Accordingly, the activation energies for scale oxidation were 609 KJ/mol from scale thickening, and 542 KJ/mol based on weight gain. The exhibited activation energies are ascribed to inward diffusion through short circuit paths which are continually evolving due to ongoing phase transformations.

Keywords: oxidation, kinetics, ceramic composites

1. INTRODUCTION

Whisker reinforced alumina is a serious candidate for high temperature applications due to its improved mechanical properties. This composite system has been widely studied [1-5] and is currently used in applications such as cutting tools [6]. Among the properties that are considerably upgraded compared with monolithic ceramics are toughness [1,2], creep [3,4], thermal shock [5], and wear [6]. Nevertheless, these composites are susceptible to environmental degradation when exposed to oxidants [7-11], or reducing atmospheres [12]. Moreover, the reaction products are not thermodynamically stable in the surrounding alumina matrix. Hence, additional reactions are found to occur in this composite. In particular, when whisker reinforced alumina is exposed to oxidizing gases, concomitant reactions occur which include the development of mullite and aluminosilicate phases.

A number of articles are currently available on the oxidation kinetics of SiC-reinforced alumina [7-11]. These reports indicate that the rate of scale thickening is essentially parabolic, with the parabolic constants diminishing at higher whisker contents [7]. Also, there is a wide variation in the reported activation energies for the oxidation process which oscillate between 350-919 KJ/mol [7,9]. In composites containing relatively low volume fractions of whiskers, inward oxygen diffusion through the alumina phase has been suggested as the rate controlling mechanism [8]. Alternatively, at relatively high SiC volume fractions, CO gas permeation and oxygen transport through silica have been suggested to be concurrent controlling processes [11]. In

addition to that, relatively large volume increases accompany the oxidation reaction. Hence, despite the number of published reports on the thermal oxidation of SiC-reinforced Al_2O_3 , there is no complete agreement on the proposed mechanisms.

In the present work, an attempt is made to provide further insight into the mechanistic aspects associated with the oxidation process. In particular, the morphological evolution of the scale, as well as the influence of continuous phase changes on the oxidation kinetics, is discussed in light of the experimental outcome.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The SiC whisker reinforced Al_2O_3 containing 30 vol% whiskers was supplied in the form of slabs by Advanced Composite Materials. The oxidation experiments were carried out by exposing specimens of 6 x 6 x 3 mm to air between 1300°C and 1500°C for various periods of time. Weight changes as a function of time and temperature were systematically measured in a highly sensitive microbalance. This was complemented by scale thickness measurements using optical means. The scale thickness was measured from the external scale surface to the inner surface which separates a dark boundary layer from the unreacted matrix. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was used to investigate the morphological changes occurring in the scale regions, whereas X-ray diffraction was used for evaluations of the scale composition.

3. RESULTS

Figure 1 shows weight gain versus time curves at various temperatures indicative of parabolic behavior. From these results, parabolic rate constants, expressed on a mass gain basis (K_m), were determined as a function of temperature. Further confirmation of a parabolic trend was provided by measurements of scale thickness with time. Figure 2 shows linear plots of scale thickness squared versus time in agreement with the parabolic rate law $x^2 = K_p t$. Since the oxidation reaction is thermally activated, activation energies were measured from Arrhenius plots of the reaction constants K_p and K_m with $1/T$ for temperatures of 1300-1500°C, respectively (Fig. 3). The activation energies found by these means were 609 KJ/mol for the rate of scale thickening, and 542 KJ/mol on the basis of mass gain. The exhibited activation energies were slightly higher than those reported for composites of similar composition [8,9]. Nevertheless, they are in good agreement considering that activation energies of up to 919 KJ/mol have been reported [7].

The scale crosssection consisted of two distinctive regions — a white porous scale with relatively large interconnected pores and an inner region known as the dark reaction layer (Fig. 4). This layer was found to exist between the completely oxidized porous scale and the unreacted composite. X-ray diffraction analyses indicated that the scale consisted mainly of mullite with SiC absent in the surface scale. Also, EDX maps indicated a uniform distribution of Al and Si (Fig. 5) in the scale. Other phases were also present but they could not be identified by these means. In particular, neither how much of the scale was an aluminosilicate nor the amount of amorphous silica in the scale was clear.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Kinetics

The oxidation of SiC reinforced alumina can be described by the following sequence of reactions:

Oxidation of SiC whiskers

Formation of an aluminosilicate phase

Formation of mullite

Oxidation of graphitic carbon

From these reactions, it is clear that SiC has to be oxidized before any other reactions can be activated. Thus, the driving force for the oxidation reaction is the oxygen chemical potential gradient existing between the white scale surface and the SiC-SiO₂ interface

$$\mu = \mu_o + RT \ln \left[\frac{P_{\text{O}_2}^*}{P_{\text{O}_2}} \right] \quad (5)$$

where $P_{\text{O}_2}^*$ is the equilibrium oxygen pressure at the SiC/SiO₂ interface, and P_{O_2} is the oxygen partial pressure in air. Moreover, the rate of scale growth including the dark reaction layer can be formulated as

$$\frac{d[x + \xi]}{dt} = \frac{K_p}{[x + \xi]} \quad (6)$$

where K_p and ξ are independent of time, and ξ is the dark layer thickness. Integration of this expression gives rise to the well known parabolic law for scale growth.

$$[x + \xi]^2 = 2K_p t \quad (7)$$

where K_p is related to the effective diffusivity of oxidant D_{ef} through the white and dark scale regions, and it can be given by

$$K_p = \frac{2D_{ef}C_o}{\rho} \quad (8)$$

where C_o is the concentration of oxidant at the scale/air interface, and ρ is the density of oxidant incorporated in the reaction product.

The experimental outcome of this work indicated that parabolic behavior was exhibited in agreement with published reports [7-11]. Moreover, the parabolic constants and the activation energies are consistent with those found by other workers [7-10]. Although scaling in SiC-reinforced alumina is essentially parabolic, the mechanisms so far proposed are limited to cases where alumina is the dominant path for inward diffusion of oxygen [8]. Nevertheless, the exhibited activation energies are not simply related to a unique transport mechanism. Continuous phase changes in the dark reaction layer lead to the development of short circuit paths which might become rate limiting at different stages during the oxidation process. This makes it difficult to define a single mechanism. Apparently, oxidation starts at the matrix/dark layer interface where alumina is the dominant oxygen transport path. But it is brought to completion at the white scale/dark layer interface where either mullite, amorphous silica, or aluminosilicate phases might control the effective oxygen diffusivity. Since at a given temperature the dark layer region reaches a constant value independent of time [8], the oxidation mechanisms can be explained by further examining this region.

The series of events occurring in the dark layer region can be qualitatively described by considering a single whisker in a uniform distribution. Assuming that inward oxygen diffusion through the oxidation product is rate limiting, partly oxidized whiskers, as well as new phases are built within the dark layer. Accordingly, oxidation of freshly exposed SiC_w starts upon oxygen arrival at the dark layer/matrix interface. Here, oxygen diffusion through the alumina matrix is expected to be dominant. Once oxidation has started, an amorphous silica envelope forms around SiC_w which is accompanied by a large volume increase. An estimation of the magnitude of the volume expansion yields values of up to 100% for systems containing over 60 vol% SiC [7].

As the oxidation reaction proceeds further, the diffusion path is modified to include oxygen transport through the SiO₂ envelope. Since the silica phase is not thermodynamically stable in the surrounding alumina, additional phase transformations are activated. From equilibrium thermodynamics, mullite and alumina are expected to be the final structures for composites with less than 24.9 vol% SiC_w and mullite plus silica for SiC > 24.9 vol%. However, liquid aluminosilicates or glassy phases of unidentified composition are also present [7-9]. These additional phases provide fast paths for oxygen arrival at the SiC/SiO₂ interface and can become rate controlling. These continuous events are expected to take place at different stages during oxidation until total consumption of SiC occurs at the white scale/dark layer interface. Since the oxygen diffusion path is continually changing in this region, it is expected that the activation energies will reflect these effects. This explains the wide variations reported in experimentally determined activation energies for composites with similar whisker contents.

The oxidation of SiC reinforced Al₂O₃ can also be rate controlled by the oxidation of graphitic carbon. Experimentally, it has been observed [7] that the concentration of deposited carbon reaches a maximum half way between the outer and inner interfaces of the dark layer region.

Also, the carbon concentration falls to zero at the inner end of the white scale interface. The lack of carbon in the white scale region suggests that the development of the white scale/dark scale interface is closely linked to the oxidation of graphitic carbon. Hence, it is likely that as the concentration of graphitic carbon in the dark reaction layer increases, it becomes rate limiting. As graphitic carbon is oxidized, permeation of molecular CO through amorphous silica will be the effective transport mechanism. However, at the inner interface of the dark layer region, oxidation of graphitic carbon might be limited by insufficient silica for CO permeation. Accordingly, it is expected that near the white scale/dark scale interface, the incoming oxygen will be effectively consumed by the CO reaction whereas deep in the dark layer SiC oxidation will be dominant.

The effect of increasing volume fractions of SiC on lowering the oxidation rates [7,8] can be explained by the development of relatively large volumes of amorphous silica. This, in association with enough graphitic carbon, favors the CO reaction and limits the amount of oxygen available for the oxidation of SiC. Also, the diffusion path contribution through SiO₂ might become dominant, leading to further reduction in oxidation rates. Finally, the absence of pores in the dark region indicates that the surface tension forces are not overcome by the resultant CO pressure. Thus, molecular gas permeation is the predominant CO degassing mechanism in this region. Nevertheless, in the white scale, the exhibited porosity indicates that in this region P_{CO} often exceeds $2 \gamma/r$ required for the nucleation of CO bubbles.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the oxidation kinetics of a 30 vol% SiC-alumina was investigated. Activation energies of 609 KJ/mol based on scale thickness measurements and 542 KJ/mol based on weight gain changes were found which are consistent with those reported in the literature. However, the activation energies cannot be ascribed to a single transport mechanism. Although X-ray diffraction studies indicated that the scale was predominantly mullite, glassy phases were also present. Two distinguishable regions were observed in the scale cross-section — an external scale which was highly porous, and a dark scale layer. Since concomitant oxidation and phase changes are occurring here, a qualitative mechanism was proposed where the effective diffusion path is continually altered across this region. Finally, it is suggested that the oxidation of graphitic carbon is also influenced by the surrounding phases in the dark reaction layer. In the inner reaction front, alumina is the dominant phase and CO permeation is limited. However, half-way in the dark reaction layer enough silica forms to provide a path for CO permeation.

6. REFERENCES

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Fig. 1. Typical plots of mass gain versus time at various temperatures for 30 vol% SiC-Al₂O₃ composite.

Fig. 2. Scale thickness squared versus time at various temperatures for 30 vol% SiC-Al₂O₃ composite.

Fig. 3. Arrhenius plots based on parabolic constants as a function of scale thickness (K_p), and mass gain (K_m) for 30 vol% SiC-Al₂O₃ composite.

Fig. 4. Optical micrograph of scale cross section showing a highly porous white scale region and an inner dark layer in contact with the unreacted matrix.

a

b

Fig. 5. EdX maps of surface scale composition after air exposure for 25 hours at 1500°C. (a) Si map, and (b) Al map.

CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES: PROCESSING

